

Political Preconditions for National Values of the Kazakhstan Nation

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Abstract—Article is devoted to the problem of Kazakhstan people national values in the conditions of the Republic of Kazakhstan independence. Formation of ethnos national values is viewed as the mandatory constituent of this process in contemporary conditions. The article shows the dynamics of forming social-spiritual basis of Kazakhstan people's national values. It depicts peculiarities of interethnic relations in poly-ethnic and multiconfessional Kazakhstan.

The study reviews in every detail various directions of the state social policy development in the sphere of national values. It is aimed to consolidation of the society to achieve the shared objective, i.e. building democratic and civilized state.

The author discloses peculiarities of ethnos national values development using specific sources. It is underlined that renewal and modernization of Kazakhstan society represents new stage in the national value development, and its typical feature is integration process based on peoples' friendship, cultural principles of interethnic communication.

Keywords—Interethnic relation, Kazakhstan people, national policy, national values.

I. INTRODUCTION

STATE social policy is one of the governmental activities aimed at regulating national value of Kazakhstan nation. The essence of this policy consists in maintaining friendly relations between ethnic groups to provide conditions for preserving national or ethnic values of the peoples living in Kazakhstan.

At contemporary stage the process of mankind development is inseparably linked with national values of the nationalities. Neither of political, national or interethnic problems is impossible to solve without consideration of this link.

The problem of ethnos national values holds a prominent place among other problems of multinational society development defined by a complicated and contradictory character. At contemporary stage the study of ethnic groups' national values claims special attention. The content of the peoples' national values is defined by the production method of material and nonmaterial benefits and the type of social relations. Ethnic groups' national values constitute specific law of the national relations development, and determine mutual approach and respect of nations, ethnic group and also countries. Investigation of this problem is very important and vital for multinational and multiconfessional Republic of Kazakhstan.

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Thus the problem of national values of the peoples represents complicated and multifaceted phenomenon that requires close attention and study. Therefore the researchers face the tasks of comprehensive study of new phenomena and the processes of the peoples' national values that take place in their lives, and theoretical justification which can promote solution of the urgent political problems. It should be observed that the problem of the peoples' national values including those of Kazakhstan people has not been investigated sufficiently in the studies of the scientists and primarily politologists as a separate research.

Future prospects of our country depend on scientific learning of the national policy and our perception of the role of ethnic groups' national values in the society development. So integrated approach is required to exclusively important and not studied issues of ethnic groups' national values in the conditions of transition to the market economy. At present, when contradictions in inter-ethnic relationships reached the dangerous line in various parts of the world, the study of the above indicated problem is caused by the objective need of strengthening peoples' friendship and deepening integration processes and search for new forms of mutual assistance and cooperation development of the nationalities and the states in the period of social life renewal and democratization.

The aim of this article is to trace how the population of Kazakhstan being a part of the Russian Empire for a long period of time was transformed from the state with overall soviet value into a state with national values on the basis of the theoretical and practical researches. The article shows that Kazakhstan society is diversified in ethnic, cultural, confessional and other respects, but it is united by the common history and destiny. Therefore the essence of the Kazakhstani ethnic groups' national values consists in historical memory that keeps gratitude to Kazakh people and Kazakh land for help and support provided at the crucial moment of the history.

II. SOCIAL SPIRITUAL FOUNDATION OF KAZAKHSTAN NATIONAL VALUE FORMATION

Social and spiritual foundations of Kazakhstan ethnic groups' national values are aimed at the society uniting and consolidation to achieve the common aim, i.e. building democratic and civilized state. It should be underlined that formation of the Kazakhstan people's national value is possible only on the basis of the national and overall Kazakhstan pride that presupposes the actual equality between the ethnic groups of Kazakhstan. It is caused by the unity and

consolidation of the scientific outlook of all Kazakhstan citizens.

Spiritual grounds of ethnic groups' national values mean desire and ability of the social strata to jointly solve cultural and political problems existing in the Republic. In this regard the state policy ensures regulation of those phenomena and processes that promote formation of ethnic groups' national values in the country. The basis of this policy is first of all the strengthening of the country's economic basis that ensures the growth of material welfare of all ethnic groups that compose Kazakhstan society. This is confirmed by the RK President's Letter that reads the following: We have definitely specified our plans of the economy industrialization and technological development. The main aim of our programs is to secure the well-being of our people. Therefore in this Letter I devote special attention to the issues of social modernization. I have approved three main state programs: development of education, healthcare and languages. These programs are aimed at solution of the daily problems of millions of ordinary people of the country. They will improve the life quality of Kazakhstan citizens [1].

Securing Kazakhstan ethnic groups' national values is the main condition of developing and implementing strategic tasks of social-economic and political modernization of the country. Our great aim is to preserve national values of the peoples and become great nation irrespective of the ethnic origin by saving and handing over the most precious that we possess, it's our sovereign and independent Kazakhstan. Doctrine of Kazakhstan national unity reads as follows: for the sake of this aim we have to overcome all prejudices and artificial hindrances that hinder our unity. That means that every citizen, society and the state should comprehend their responsibility before the people and future generations and take all measures to provide:

1. Active confrontation to any influence that disunites us and disintegrates our unity;
2. Further strengthening of economic, political safety and spiritual sovereignty of the country; prohibition of information dependency of Kazakhstan, information expansion or blockade on the part of other states;
3. Further consolidation of all citizens of Kazakhstan around the Kazakh people aimed at independence of the state;
4. Careful attitude to our main wealth, namely independence, land, unity and spirituality» [2].

The aim of this Doctrine is to define priorities and leverages of securing national values of Kazakhstan ethnic groups on the basis of civil identity, patriotism of spiritual-cultural community, stability preservation and inter-ethnic and inter-confessional reconciliation of the society. National values of the Republic ethnic groups implies integrity of ethnic communities existence as part of integral state, high degree of self identification of the citizens with the Republic of Kazakhstan and existing system of values and ideals.

The basis of the Kazakhstan society ethnic groups is the identity of values that are close to the absolute majority of Kazakhstan people, and consolidate the society into the whole

unity. Our common history is the consolidating principle and the deserved pride of all generations of Kazakhstan people.

Since gaining the independence free choice of personal fortune, involvement in the new state building, joint responsibility for the country destiny and future generations have become the common values of Kazakhstan people. High level of tolerance to way of life, customs, feelings, opinions, ideas and religious faiths of all ethnic groups, confessions and social groups is inherent for Kazakhstan people. At the same time national values of ethnic cultures of Kazakhstan are the source of constant enrichment and development of all Kazakhstan people.

Moral values, deference to the older generation, respect to family institution and tradition of hospitality have deeply seated in the Kazakhstani society. All this contributes to strengthening of mutual understanding and friendship of citizens of different ethnic and religious affiliation. To achieve the purpose in view it is required to concentrate efforts of forming the state national value on solution of the following tasks:

- Strengthening general Kazakhstani identity, consensus support of the main values of Kazakhstan society;
- Formation of the efficient system of national values in the sphere of inter-ethnic and inter-confessional relations;
- Development of the state official language as the factor of the national value of Kazakhstan people unity;
- Promotion of saving and development of ethnic cultural and linguistic identity of Kazakhstan ethnic groups;
- Resistance actions against extremism and radicalism manifestations, non-admission of human rights and liberties impairment and violation based on formation of ethnic groups' national values.

The present program representing combination of the basic setups, approaches and guiding lines of the state policy in the sphere of national values is implemented on the basis of the following principles:

- Equality of human rights and liberties of citizens irrespective of ethnic affiliation;
- Prohibition of citizens' rights restriction on the grounds of social and ethnic affiliation;
- Suppression of activity aimed at inciting social, ethnic and religious discord, diminishing the state security;
- Respect of the state language and its role in the society;
- Respect of national traditions, promotion to development of ethnic cultures and languages;
- Protection of rights and interests of Kazakhstan citizens abroad, support of compatriots living in foreign countries in preservation and development of the native language, culture and traditions and strengthening their ties with historical homeland.

The state activity in this sphere will be aimed to securing efficient involvement of Assembly of Nations of Kazakhstan, ethnic-cultural associations and other institutions of the civil society in implementing state policy regarding national values.

Measures should be taken that are aimed to inclusion of citizens in inter-ethnic integration and traditions of Kazakhstan society under conditions of cultural identity

preservation of all ethnic groups. In order to implement and improve these measures, conditions should be created for strengthening the Kazakhstani family institution, its educational role in the sphere of national traditions preservation and development, development of tolerant and respectful attitude of the youngster generation to cultural traditions, language and national values of all ethnic groups living in Kazakhstan. National theatres and creative teams should be provided support and assistance. Cultural-educating institutions should stimulate their activities aimed to preserving historic and cultural heritage of the Kazakh nation, further mutual enrichment of ethnic cultures. Intercultural dialogue and humanitarian cooperation should be developed with countries of Kazakh expat community residence and also with countries being the historical homeland of Kazakhstan ethnic groups. Implementation of these measures will enable to preserve and develop national values of the Republic, and further implement the formula “national values of ethnic groups through diversity unity”.

This important and needful political measures have been originated by the serious concern arisen by the process of national values peoples’ cultures unification, loss of national roots and languages, assimilation of small nations taking pace around the world. But the mankind will survive not only due to universal values, but due to those national values that are shared by only several thousands or hundreds of people. Therefore ethnos national values are called to reverse these processes by telling everybody about the importance of the specific value, which is authentic treasury of the nation’s spirit to be carefully treated with respect and love. It ought to take thought today what we can do to keep national values of each ethnic group for the benefit of Kazakhstan and the whole planet.

III. EDUCATION OF KAZAKHSTAN PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF NATIONAL VALUES OF EACH ETHNIC GROUP

One of the major factors for ensuring national value of each Kazakhstan ethnos is education and bringing up younger generation by the example of tolerance and consensus. The scientists dealing with this problem face challenges of comprehensive study of new phenomena and processes occurring in the life of each nation and bringing up Kazakhstani people in the spirit of ethnos friendship. These phenomena require theoretical generalization, which could promote to solve vital practical issues of Kazakhstan nations’ values.

Kazakhstani experience demonstrates that education of the population in the spirit of national value of each ethnos comprises specific historical and social political content. The problem of educational process of Kazakhstani citizens presupposes new scientific apprehension of the historic truth and national phenomena with account of Kazakhstani interests. Historical experience helps to bring people up on working, combat, Kazakhstani and international traditions of multinational Kazakhstan.

By drawing the moral from the past we should use all forms and methods to improve education of Kazakhstan people using

the principles of national values and raise them on new level. The main thing is to achieve the complete harmony of interests of all ethnic needs, as well as tolerance, adherence to unity and variety of the national cultures, languages and traditions. In this respect the Government has taken a number of measures:

1. This means that we should be the community of well-consolidated ethnic, religious and other social-cultural groups living in our country. In contemporary world the national value is defined by such conditions as joint creation of the common state, tolerance, stability and inter-ethnic consensus;

2. Why should we strengthen national values of ethnic groups? In this respect we have agreement of opinion. It can be expressed as one notion, that is unanimity inside the country. External safety depends on this factor. The main thing is progressive advance of the country and hence our well-being and prosperity;

3. What is the main national value? The national value of Kazakhstan people is reposed on three main pillars:

- Our common history;
- Values being common for all ethnic groups;
- Our common future.

Now one should mention some specific objectives for future. In order to strengthen potential of the ethnic groups’ national values it is expedient to implement a number of measures in the following directions.

First, it is primarily necessary to develop national identity, tolerance in the Kazakhstan society via the system of education and upbringing, correct coverage of the national ethnos value in mass media and increase of legal culture of Kazakhstan citizens. Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan should develop conceptual proposal for development of ethnic and poly-cultural education with an allowance for specific character of Kazakhstan society. It is desirable to develop and introduce in schools and higher institutions the mandatory course “Fundamental principles of the national values of Kazakhstan ethnic groups”.

The second direction consists in further development of the state language. To achieve this it is necessary to consistently implement range of requisite measures without diminishing one nation and exalting another. State language is the main factor of the people’s national value. In this regard the state language development should not result in discrimination caused by poor proficiency of this language. Violation of our citizens’ constitutional rights is not permissible, and must be immediately suppressed by law-enforcement authorities.

Third, the important constituent of ethnos national value is interethnic concord in our society. Principle of legislative equality and religions interaction exists in Kazakhstan. Moslem Spiritual Administration of Kazakhstan is the largest confession. Similar moral educational work is expected from other confessions of Kazakhstan.

The fourth, strength of the people national values is directly linked with increasing performance efficiency of Assembly of Kazakhstan People (APK). First of all it is necessary to intensify coordinating role of APK Secretariat and Scientific and Expert Council. It is necessary to establish a grant for

scientists conducting applied research of ethnos national value issues.

The fifth, Kazakhstan model of ethnos national values should be wider spread around the world. With this objective in view it is important to use experience of Kazakhstan chairmanship in Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) and the current chairmanship in Organization of the Islamic Conference and Shanghai Cooperation Organization. APK and all National Culture Associations of Kazakhstan should take an active part in this work.

Thus, what is the essence of creating this original and unique Kazakhstan model of the ethnos national values, when variegated and diversified ethnic, cultural multi-confessional society is so unified? The indicated model has been able to reconcile and unite into integrated whole extremely contradictive factors of human existence. On the one hand, Kazakhstan is a poly-ethnic country inhabited by representatives of 140 ethnic groups; on the other hand, this is an unitarian state. On the one hand, the name of the state, its essence is defined by the Kazakhs, the nation related to statehood development; on the other hand each specific ethnos is permitted to implement its interests through national values of each Kazakhstan ethnic group.

Striving for political and civil unity leads to situation, when Kazakhstan becomes the community of citizens belonging to various ethnic groups. The Kazakhs are consolidated nation. Kazakhstan independence is the merited right of the Kazakhs to build their statehood on their ancient native land. This is an unconditional historical fact. Respect to this aspiration of the Kazakh nation to revive its culture and history and national identity on behalf of various ethnic groups is the strategic basis of the country stability and condition of peace and concord. After all the considerable portion of Kazakhstan history consisted of ethnic and cultural interactions of various ethnic groups inhabited this land. Following independence all Kazakhstan citizens live in one political, economic and cultural space and nationwide cultural space is being successfully formed [3].

The important direction in this respect and major factor of securing national values is the education of the younger generation of Kazakhstan citizens in the spirit of tolerance and consensus. The following actions are to be taken in this direction:

- Develop the Program of ethnic-cultural education intended for all levels of continuous education and so on;
- Introduce interactive methods of studying ethnic-cultural values, formation of stable positive stereotypes in relation to representatives of another cultural environment in preschool, secondary level, vocational technical educational institutions and higher education establishments;
- Creation of conditions for teaching in schools the training course "Fundamentals of National Values" in order to increase information awareness and educational level of the younger generation as for Kazakhstan people's national values are concerned;

- Educators' skills improvement and their supply with teaching materials on the problems of national values and interethnic intercourse;

- Assistance provision in development and purchasing education materials and teaching aids, distribution of publications and printed sources, broadcasting radio and television programs in languages of the ethnic groups in the areas of their compact settlement;

- Development of network of school museums of historic and combat glory of Kazakhstan peoples;

- Expansion of real interaction of school teachers and pupils' parents via out-of-school activities of ethnic-cultural education, formation of civil position and national values of Kazakhstan people;

- Initiation of annual patriotic action: "Kazakhstan is my motherland" associated with the day of Kazakhstan people unity and aimed to the society consolidation and strengthening of Kazakhstan people national values.

The indicated measures should facilitate further strengthening among younger generation of ideas and traditions of Kazakhstan national values.

Proclamation of polyethnic population as a single Kazakhstan nation and intention to form corresponding identity is the fundamentally new idea in the national policy of the contemporary Kazakhstan. Such strategy is conceptually based on and inspired by idea of national value. Mainly patriotism legitimated as the society's cultural and historic tradition being ultimately of ethnic origin is an institutional and ideological expression of the values created by ethnic groups irrespective of etatistic national value attitudes.

Based on the above mentioned one can make a conclusion that the national value of Kazakhstan people is not only the issue of theoretical discussions but also the issue of the practice daily implemented by the state policy. This is the issue of the national security. Efficiency of this policy is proved by the reduction of emigration from Kazakhstan that was typical for the period of the Soviet Union collapse, and remigration. Emigration at the late 1980s-early 1990s did not provoke political collisions. Legal base is created in Kazakhstan to preserve and revive national values of each Kazakhstan nation, ethnic self-expression and development. For this purpose newspapers are published in national languages and TV and radio programs are broadcasted. All this contributes to preservation and development of each ethnos national values.

IV. CONCLUSION

Retention of Kazakhstan people national values represents the leading factor of the country stable development. National values have become the required constituent of peace and unity. National values are formed via unity of all ethnic groups on the basis of moral-cultural and civil alliance upon consolidating role of the state language and culture of the Kazakh nation. The role of Assembly of Kazakhstan People is very prominent in this respect, this Assembly is a public institution involved in regulating interethnic relations and retention of the ethnos national values.

Retention of the Kazakhstan people national values is the important condition of democratic, secular, legal and social state formation. Economic growth, social progress and democratic development of the country are possible only upon retention and development of the Kazakhstan society national values. To implement this important task Kazakhstan as independent and sovereign state recognized around the world possesses all necessary economic, social and political resources.

Doctrine of Kazakhstan National Unity promotes to implement the assigned task; its objective is to create integral system of judicial, socio-economic, political and state managerial measures aimed at strengthening national values of each ethnos of the Republic. Implementation of this document is accomplished by mobilization and activation of human and intellectual potential of the country for the purpose of accelerated development of Kazakhstan, achievement of the worthwhile living standards for each Kazakhstan citizen and observation and protection rights and freedoms ensured by the Constitution [4].

Accordingly retention and development of Kazakhstan people national values mean institutionalization of the national policy. Kazakhstan experience of ethnopolitics is extremely important. Institutionalization means practical implementation; it is not only proclamation and other verbal forms of national policy expression, but its practical realization through political will of the leadership and primarily the National Leader N.A.Nazarbaev applying specific leverages.

This refers to the complicated sphere of political society activity, i.e. social-political participation of ethnic groups; the significance of this is mentioned in Lund Recommendations on the Effective Participation of the National Minorities in Public Life developed by international experts under the auspice of OSCE High Commissioner on National minorities [5]. Republic of Kazakhstan to the full extent secures the rights and national values of all ethnic groups living in Kazakhstan in compliance with international standards on human rights.

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